

Bias in Human Origins Research

Supplementary Information

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4. School of Physics, Chemistry and Earth Sciences, University of Adelaide, Australia
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6. Queensland Museum, Brisbane, Australia
7. School of Archaeology and Anthropology, The Australian National University, Canberra, Australia
8. Department of Archaeology, Max Planck Institute for Geoanthropology, Jena, Germany
9. School of Social Science, University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia
10. School of Environment and Science, Griffith University, Brisbane, Australia
11. Monash Indigenous Studies Centre, Monash University, Clayton campus, Australia
12. Australian Research Council Centre of Excellence for Australian Biodiversity and Heritage (CABAH), Monash University, Australia
13. College of Arts and Social Sciences, Australian National University, Canberra, Australian Capital Territory, Australia
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15. Palaeo-Research Institute, University of Johannesburg, Gaunteng, South Africa
16. School of Archaeology, University of the Philippines, Philippines
17. Earth Sciences Department, National Museums of Kenya, Nairobi, Kenya
18. Human Origins Program, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, DC, USA
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21. National Centre for Indigenous Genomics, John Curtin School of Medical Research, Australian National University, Canberra, Australian Capital Territory, Australia
22. Indigenous Genomics, Telethon Kids Institute, Adelaide, South Australia, Australia
23. National Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH), Burgos, Spain
24. Atmospheric Observations Research Group, University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia
25. College of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences, Flinders University, Adelaide, Australia
26. School of Earth and Atmospheric Sciences, Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, Australia
27. School of Culture, History and Language, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia
28. Centre for Heritage and Museum Studies, College of Arts and Social Sciences, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia
29. Northern Institute, Faculty of Arts and Social Science, Charles Darwin University, Darwin, Australia Archaeology/Centre for Rock Art Research and Management, School of Social Sciences, University of Western Australia, Crawley, Australia
30. King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia
31. Department of History and Archaeology, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka

32. Key Laboratory of Vertebrate Evolution and Human Origins, Institute of Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China
33. State Key Laboratory of Lithospheric and Environmental Coevolution, Institute of Geology and Geophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China
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Affiliation data

Africa

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND evolution* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo*and AND dispersal* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND dispersal* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND fossil* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND fossil* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archaeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND africa*)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART"))

Table S1 Author affiliation counts per institution listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Africa. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

AFFILIATION	COUNT	COUNTRY
University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg	80	South Africa
CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	70	France
University of Cape Town	50	South Africa
Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	35	France
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	34	Germany
University of Cambridge	32	UK
University of Oxford	32	UK
University of Johannesburg	30	South Africa
Université de Bordeaux	28	France
Max-Planck-Institut für Evolutionäre Anthropologie	28	Germany
The Australian National University	27	Australia
University of Wollongong	27	Australia
De la Préhistoire à l'Actuel Culture, Environnement et Anthropologie	26	France
University College London	24	UK
Harvard University	23	US
Stanford University	23	US
University of South Africa	22	South Africa
Arizona State University	21	US
Universitetet i Bergen	20	Norway
University of Pretoria	20	South Africa

University of California, Berkeley	20	US
Senckenberg Centre for Human Evolution and Palaeoenvironment	17	Germany
University of KwaZulu-Natal	17	South Africa
Stony Brook University	16	US
Stellenbosch University	15	South Africa
North-West University	15	US
Chinese Academy of Sciences	14	China
Aix Marseille Université	14	France
Sorbonne Université	14	France
University of the Western Cape	14	South Africa
Institute of Human Origins	14	US
Yale University	14	US
The University of Queensland	13	Australia
National Museums of Kenya	13	Kenya
Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana CENIEH	13	Spain
Instituto Catalán de Paleoecología Humana y Evolución Social	13	Spain
King's College London	13	UK
The Natural History Museum, London	13	UK
Pennsylvania State University	13	US
Smithsonian Institution	13	US
University of Wisconsin-Madison	13	US
Max-Planck-Institut für Menschheitsgeschichte	12	Germany
Hebrew University of Jerusalem	12	Israel
Universidad Complutense de Madrid	12	Spain
Oxford Social Sciences Division	12	UK
The University of Arizona	12	US
University of California, Davis	12	US
The University of Sydney	11	Australia
Institute of Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology Chinese Academy of Sciences	11	China
Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History	11	US
Griffith University	10	Australia
Universität zu Köln	10	Germany
Russian Academy of Sciences	10	Russia
Nelson Mandela University	10	South Africa
Boston University	10	US
Southern Methodist University	10	US
The George Washington University	10	US
University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign	10	US
University of Michigan, Ann Arbor	10	US
KU Leuven	9	Belgium
Archéologies et Sciences de l'Antiquité	9	France
Université Paris Nanterre	9	France
University of Ghana	9	Ghana
Sapienza Università di Roma	9	Italy
Universiteit Leiden	9	Netherlands
University of the Free State	9	South Africa
University of Liverpool	9	UK
Emory University	9	US
University of California, Santa Barbara	9	US
University of Pennsylvania	9	US

Institut de Recherches sur les Archéomatériaux	8	France
Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main	8	Germany
Universidade do Algarve	8	Portugal
Iziko South African Museum	8	South Africa
Universitat Rovira i Virgili	8	Spain
University of Dar es Salaam	8	Tanzania
Duke University	8	UK
University of Bristol	8	UK
University of Pittsburgh	8	UK
University of Southampton	8	UK
New York University	8	US
The University of Chicago	8	US
University of California, Los Angeles	8	US
University of Colorado Boulder	8	US
University of Minnesota Twin Cities	8	US
University of Toronto	7	Canada
Université Bordeaux Montaigne	7	France
Heidelberger Akademie der Wissenschaften	7	Germany
University of Ibadan	7	Nigeria
Universidade de Coimbra	7	Portugal
Universidade de Lisboa	7	Portugal
Rhodes University	7	South Africa
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	7	Spain
Peabody Essex Museum	7	UK
Royal Holloway, University of London	7	UK
The University of Edinburgh	7	UK
University of Kent	7	UK
University of Leicester	7	UK
American Museum of Natural History	7	US
Michigan State University	7	US
Stanford University School of Medicine	7	US
Texas A&M University	7	US
University of Connecticut	7	US
University of Louisville	7	US
University of Washington	7	US
Monash University	6	Australia
Musée de l'Homme	6	France
Universität Zürich	6	Germany
Tel Aviv University	6	Japan
The University of Tokyo	6	Japan
Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	6	Russia
University of the Witwatersrand Faculty of Health Sciences	6	South Africa
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	6	Spain
Uppsala Universitet	6	Sweden
Liverpool John Moores University	6	UK
Columbia University	6	US
Indiana University Bloomington	6	US
Princeton University	6	US
Purdue University	6	US
The University of New Mexico	6	US
The University of Texas at Austin	6	US
The University of Utah	6	US
University of California, San Francisco	6	US

University of Notre Dame	6	US
Washington University in St. Louis	6	US
La Trobe University	5	Australia
Queen's University	5	Canada
Addis Ababa University	5	Ethiopia
Anthropologie bio-culturelle, Droit, Éthique & Santé	5	France
Commissariat a l'Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives	5	France
IRD Institut de Recherche pour le Developpement	5	France
Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional	5	Indonesia
Università di Pisa	5	Italy
University of Ferrara	5	Italy
Kyoto University	5	Japan
University of Ilorin	5	Nigeria
Universitetet i Oslo	5	Norway
Institute of Archaeology and Ethnography of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	5	Russia
Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats	5	Spain
Universitat Pompeu Fabra Barcelona	5	Spain
Lunds Universitet	5	Sweden
Aberystwyth University	5	UK
London School of Economics and Political Science	5	UK
SOAS University of London	5	UK
The University of Manchester	5	UK
The University of Sheffield	5	UK
University of Exeter	5	UK
University of Hull	5	UK
University of Reading	5	UK
Binghamton University State University of New York	5	US
Johns Hopkins University	5	US
University of Alberta	5	US
University of California, Irvine	5	US
University of California, Santa Cruz	5	US
University of Florida	5	US
Institut de Paléontologie Humaine	4	France
Universiteit van Amsterdam	4	Netherlands
Florida State University	4	US
University of Calgary	4	US
TOTAL AFFILIATIONS	1793	

Asia

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND evolution* AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND dispersal AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND fossil* AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hominin AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hominid AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND asia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND asia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human AND dispersal AND asia)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART"))

Table S2 Author affiliation counts per institution listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Asia. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

AFFILIATION	COUNT	COUNTRY
Chinese Academy of Sciences	96	China
Russian Academy of Sciences	95	Russia
The Australian National University	90	Australia
CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	86	France
University of Cambridge	83	UK
Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	78	Russia
University College London	68	UK
Institute of Archaeology and Ethnography of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	67	Russia
Institute of Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology Chinese Academy of Sciences	59	China
Harvard University	59	US
University of Oxford	58	UK
Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	48	France
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	41	China
The University of Sydney	36	Australia
University of Wollongong	36	Australia
Griffith University	34	Australia
Max-Planck-Institut für Menschheitsgeschichte	34	Germany
The University of Queensland	32	Australia
Max-Planck-Institut für Evolutionäre Anthropologie	29	Germany
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	29	Germany
University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	29	US
Smithsonian Institution	28	US
University of Pennsylvania	27	US
The University of Arizona	27	US
Stanford University	26	US
Oxford Social Sciences Division	25	UK
Peking University	24	China
University of California, Berkeley	24	US
University of the Philippines Diliman	22	Philippines
Institute of Ethnology and Anthropology of the Russian Academy of Sciences	22	Russia
Københavns Universitet	21	Denmark

Washington University in St. Louis	21	US
University of Washington	21	US
The University of Chicago	21	US
The University of Tokyo	20	Japan
National University of Singapore	20	Singapore
Pennsylvania State University	20	US
La Trobe University	19	Australia
University of Exeter	18	UK
University of Otago	18	US
UNSW Sydney	17	Australia
Fudan University	17	China
Institute of Archaeology Russian Academy of Sciences	17	Russia
The University of Sheffield	17	UK
University of New England Australia	16	Australia
Universiteit Leiden	16	Netherlands
Peter the Great Museum of Anthropology and Ethnography	16	Russia
University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg	16	South Africa
The University of Edinburgh	16	UK
Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History	16	US
University of California, Los Angeles	16	US
University of Wisconsin-Madison	16	US
Chinese Academy of Social Sciences	15	China
Université de Bordeaux	15	France
Al Farabi Kazakh National University	15	Kazakhstan
Seoul National University	15	Korea
Altai State University, Barnaul	15	Russia
Institute for the History of Material Culture RAS	15	Russia
Durham University	15	UK
Peabody Essex Museum	15	UK
University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign	15	US
Massachusetts Institute of Technology	15	US
ARC Centre of Excellence for Australian Biodiversity and Heritage	14	Australia
KU Leuven	14	Belgium
Freie Universität Berlin	14	Germany
University of Oregon	14	US
The University of Utah	14	US
University of Michigan, Ann Arbor	14	US
Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China	13	China
Tartu Ülikool	13	Estonia
Tartu Ülikooli Genoomika Instituut	13	Estonia
National Museum of Nature and Science	13	Japan
Lomonosov Moscow State University	13	Russia
Far Eastern Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	13	Russia
The University of Manchester	13	UK
University of Pittsburgh	13	UK
University of York	13	UK
University of Colorado Boulder	13	US
Harvard Medical School	13	US
Yale University	13	US
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan	13	Uzbekistan
Monash University	12	Australia
Flinders University	12	Australia

The University of Western Australia	12	Australia
Aix Marseille Université	12	France
Universität Heidelberg	12	Germany
Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	12	Germany
Deccan College Post-Graduate and Research Institute, Pune	12	India
University of Haifa	12	Israel
V.S. Sobolev Institute of Geology and Mineralogy of the Siberian Branch of the RAS	12	Russia
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	12	Spain
Universitat Pompeu Fabra Barcelona	12	Spain
Stockholms universitet	12	Sweden
Academia Sinica Taiwan	12	Taiwan
The British Museum	12	UK
Wellcome Sanger Institute	12	UK
Royal Holloway, University of London	12	UK
University of Bristol	12	UK
Broad Institute	12	US
Cornell University	12	US
University of Toronto	12	US
University of Minnesota Twin Cities	12	US
Field Museum of Natural History	12	US
Macquarie University	11	Australia
University of Melbourne	11	Australia
Jilin University	11	China
Novosibirsk State University	11	Germany
Universitat Rovira i Virgili	11	Spain
Universidad Complutense de Madrid	11	Spain
University of Nottingham	11	UK
Faculty of Social Sciences & Health	11	UK
Princeton University	11	US
The University of Texas at Austin	11	US
Texas A&M University	11	US
University of California, Santa Barbara	11	US
National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Armenia	10	Armenia
Université de Liège	10	Belgium
Université McGill	10	Canada
Simon Fraser University	10	Canada
Yunnan University	10	China
Institute of Geology, Chinese Academy of Geological Sciences	10	China
Sorbonne Université	10	France
Senckenberg Centre for Human Evolution and Palaeoenvironment	10	Germany
Tel Aviv University	10	Israel
University of London	10	UK
Arizona State University	10	US
Universität Wien	9	Austria
University of Alberta	9	Canada
Kunming Institute of Zoology Chinese Academy of Sciences	9	China
Université Toulouse III - Paul Sabatier	9	France
Culture, Environnement et Anthropologie	9	France
Archéologies et Sciences de l'Antiquité	9	France
Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	9	Germany
Bar-Ilan University	9	Israel

Hebrew University of Jerusalem	9	Israel
Statens Naturhistoriske Museum	9	Norway
Polish Academy of Sciences	9	Poland
Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats	9	Spain
Instituto Catalán de Paleoeología Humana y Evolución Social	9	Spain
Uppsala Universitet	9	Sweden
Universität Zürich	9	Switzerland
University College Dublin	9	UK
The University of Auckland	9	UK
University of Reading	9	UK
University of Liverpool	9	UK
The Natural History Museum, London	9	UK
SOAS University of London	9	UK
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine	9	Ukraine
Northwest University	9	US
The Ohio State University	9	US
Howard Hughes Medical Institute	9	US
University of California, Davis	9	US
Boston University	9	US
New York University	9	US
Columbia University	9	US
The University of New Mexico	9	US
A.Kh. Margulan Archeology Institute	8	Kazakhstan
University of Glasgow	8	UK
University of Nevada, Reno	8	US
TOTAL AFFILIATIONS	3010	

Europe

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND evolution* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo*and AND dispersal* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND dispersal* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND fossil* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND fossil* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archaeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND europe*)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART"))

Table S3 Author affiliation counts per institution listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Europe. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

AFFILIATION	COUNT	COUNTRY
University of Cambridge	68	UK
CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	67	France
University of Oxford	58	UK
Russian Academy of Sciences	46	Russia
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	33	Germany
University of California, Berkeley	32	US
Université de Bordeaux	30	France
University College London	30	UK
The Australian National University	29	Australia
Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	26	France
Universiteit Leiden	26	Netherlands
De la Préhistoire à l'Actuel Culture, Environnement et Anthropologie	24	France
Harvard University	24	US
Stanford University	24	US
Columbia University	23	US
Københavns Universitet	22	Denmark
Universiteit van Amsterdam	22	Netherlands
The University of Manchester	22	UK
Yale University	22	US
Max-Planck-Institut für Evolutionäre Anthropologie	21	Germany
Durham University	21	UK
Universitat de Barcelona	20	Spain
The University of Edinburgh	20	UK
The University of Sydney	19	Australia
Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic	19	Czech Republic
Uniwersytet Jagielloński	19	Poland
Lomonosov Moscow State University	19	Russia
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	19	Spain
Universidad Complutense de Madrid	19	Spain

London School of Economics and Political Science	19	UK
The City University of New York	19	US
Universität zu Köln	18	German
Universität Wien	18	German
Universitat Rovira i Virgili	18	Spain
University of Bristol	18	UK
University of Pennsylvania	18	US
The University of Arizona	18	US
University of California, Los Angeles	18	US
The University of Chicago	18	US
KU Leuven	17	Belgium
Chinese Academy of Sciences	17	China
Helsingin Yliopisto	17	Finland
University of Ferrara	17	Italy
Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna	17	Italy
Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	17	Russia
University of Toronto	17	US
Aix Marseille Université	16	France
Univerza v Ljubljani	16	Slovenia
Instituto Catalán de Paleoeología Humana y Evolución Social	16	Spain
University of Reading	16	UK
University of Warsaw	16	UK
University of Warwick	16	UK
Polish Academy of Sciences	15	Poland
The University of Sheffield	15	UK
King's College London	15	UK
Charles University	15	UK
Queen Mary University of London	15	UK
Archéologies et Sciences de l'Antiquité	14	France
Freie Universität Berlin	14	Germany
Senckenberg Centre for Human Evolution and Palaeoenvironment	14	Germany
Universiteit Utrecht	14	Netherlands
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen	14	Netherlands
HSE University	14	Russia
University of Nottingham	14	UK
University of Liverpool	14	UK
Arizona State University	14	US
Johns Hopkins University	14	US
The University of Queensland	13	Australia
University of Zagreb	13	Croatia
Masaryk University	13	Czech Republic
Tel Aviv University	13	Israel
Hebrew University of Jerusalem	13	Israel
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	13	Netherlands
Saint Petersburg State University	13	Russia
Universidad de Cantabria	13	Spain
Uppsala Universitet	13	Sweden
University of Pittsburgh	13	UK
Washington University in St. Louis	13	US
University of California, Santa Barbara	13	US

Institute of Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology Chinese Academy of Sciences	12	China
Lunds Universitet	12	Denmark
University of Haifa	12	Israel
Sapienza Università di Roma	12	Italy
Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu	12	Poland
Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	12	Spain
Université de Genève	12	Switzerland
University College Dublin	12	UK
Duke University	12	UK
University of Aberdeen	12	UK
University of Notre Dame	12	UK
Pennsylvania State University	12	US
Princeton University	12	US
University of Minnesota Twin Cities	12	US
University of Wisconsin-Madison	12	US
The University of New Mexico	12	US
The University of British Columbia	11	Canada
Simon Fraser University	11	Canada
Tartu Ülikool	11	Estonia
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	11	Italy
Universitetet i Oslo	11	Norway
Universitetet i Bergen	11	Norway
Universidade de Lisboa	11	Portugal
Institute of Archaeology and Ethnography of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	11	Russia
Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana CENIEH	11	Spain
Göteborgs Universitet	11	Sweden
The Natural History Museum, London	11	UK
Queen's University Belfast	11	UK
Oxford Social Sciences Division	11	UK
University of Melbourne	10	Australia
University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences	10	Croatia
Université McGill	10	France
Ben-Gurion University of the Negev	10	Israel
European University Institute, San Domenico di Fiesole	10	Italy
University of Lodz	10	Poland
Tomsk State University	10	Russia
Moscow State Institute of International Relations MGIMO	10	Russia
Kazan Federal University	10	Russia
Slovak Academy of Sciences	10	Slovakia
University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg	10	South Africa
CSIC - Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales MNCN	10	Spain
Universidad de Alcalá	10	Spain
Instituto Internacional de Investigaciones Prehistóricas de Cantabria IIIPC	10	Spain
University of Birmingham	10	UK
University of Southampton	10	UK
University of London	10	UK
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine	10	Ukraine
University of Colorado Boulder	10	US
The Ohio State University	10	US

University of California, Irvine	10	US
University of Washington	10	US
Boston University	10	US
New York University	10	US
Monash University	9	Australia
University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign	9	France
Université Toulouse - Jean Jaurès	9	France
Université Paris Cité	9	France
Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main	9	Germany
Universität Heidelberg	9	Germany
Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	9	Germany
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	9	Greece
Magyar Tudományok Akadémia	9	Hungary
Università degli Studi di Firenze	9	Italy
Radboud Universiteit	9	Netherlands
University of Wrocław	9	Poland
RUDN University	9	Russia
National University of Singapore	9	Singapore
Newcastle University	9	UK
Cornell University	9	UK
Birkbeck, University of London	9	UK
Western University	9	UK
University of York	9	UK
University of Sussex	9	UK
Faculty of Social Sciences & Health	9	UK
University of California, Davis	9	US
Binghamton University State University of New York	9	US
Temple University	9	US
University of Alberta	9	US
Illinois State University	9	US
Sorbonne Université	8	France
University of Glasgow	8	UK
TOTAL AFFILIATIONS	2417	

Australia

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND dispersal AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND dispersal AND sahum)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART")))

Table S4 Author affiliation counts per institution listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Australia. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

AFFILIATION	COUNT	COUNTRY
The Australian National University	134	Australia
The University of Western Australia	131	Australia
Flinders University	120	Australia
The University of Queensland	87	Australia
La Trobe University	68	Australia
Monash University	61	Australia
James Cook University	60	Australia
ARC Centre of Excellence for Australian Biodiversity and Heritage	59	Australia
The University of Sydney	58	Australia
Griffith University	50	Australia
University of Wollongong	42	Australia
University of New England Australia	38	Australia
The University of Auckland	34	New Zealand
UNSW Sydney	30	Australia
Faculty of Science, Medicine and Health	29	Australia
The University of Adelaide	25	Australia
Macquarie University	24	Australia
University of Melbourne	24	Australia
University of Cambridge	20	UK
National Museum of Australia	17	Australia
Western Australian Museum	16	Australia
Curtin University	16	Australia
Australian Museum	14	Australia
University of Oxford	13	UK
Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation	12	Australia
University of York	12	UK
The University of Waikato	11	New Zealand
University of Southampton	11	US
University of Southern Queensland	10	Australia
Université Savoie Mont Blanc	10	France
Charles Darwin University	9	Australia
Queensland University of Technology	9	Australia

University of Canberra	9	Australia
CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	9	France
EDYTEM Laboratoire Environnements, Dynamiques et Territoires de la Montagne	9	France
University of Tasmania	8	Australia
Max-Planck-Institut für Menschheitsgeschichte	8	Germany
The University of Sheffield	8	UK
University of Exeter	8	UK
The University of Utah	8	US
Queensland Museum	7	Australia
The University of Notre Dame Australia	7	Australia
Université de Bordeaux	7	France
Deakin University	6	Australia
The Fenner School of Environment & Society	6	Australia
De la Préhistoire à l'Actuel Culture, Environnement et Anthropologie	6	France
Oxford Social Sciences Division	6	UK
Extent Heritage Pty Ltd	5	Australia
University of Technology Sydney	5	Australia
South Australian Museum	5	Australia
Simon Fraser University	5	Canada
Universiteit Leiden	5	Netherlands
University College London	5	UK
University of Leicester	5	UK
Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History	5	US
Harvard University	5	US
Smithsonian Institution	5	US
University of Otago	5	US
University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee	5	US
Jawoyn Association Aboriginal Corporation	4	Australia
EMM Consulting Pty Ltd	4	Australia
Southern Cross University	4	Australia
Western Sydney University	4	Australia
University of South Australia	4	Australia
University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg	4	South Africa
Universitat de Barcelona	4	Spain
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	4	Spain
University of Gloucestershire	4	UK
Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation	4	UK
RPS Group Plc	4	UK
University of Colorado Boulder	4	US
Pennsylvania State University	4	US
The University of Arizona	4	US
University of Oregon	4	US
Stanford University	4	US
University of Washington	4	US
University of Nebraska–Lincoln	4	US
University of Lincoln	4	US
University of Minnesota Twin Cities	4	US
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	3	Argentina
Kakadu National Park	3	Australia
Port Arthur Historic Site Management Authority	3	Australia
Gundjehmi Aboriginal Corporation	3	Australia

Lettuce Create	3	Australia
Murujuga Aboriginal Corporation	3	Australia
Everick Foundation	3	Australia
Archaeological and Heritage Management Solutions Pty Ltd	3	Australia
The University of Newcastle, Australia	3	Australia
RMIT University	3	Australia
The Open University	3	Australia
Murdoch University	3	Australia
School of Physics	3	Australia
School of Geography	3	Australia
College of Science and Engineering	3	Australia
John de Laeter Research Centre	3	Australia
Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle	3	France
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	3	Germany
University of Haifa	3	Israel
Hebrew University of Jerusalem	3	Israel
Universiteit van Amsterdam	3	Netherlands
University of Cape Town	3	South Africa
The University of Manchester	3	UK
University of Canterbury	3	UK
Royal Holloway, University of London	3	UK
Manchester Metropolitan University	3	UK
Brown University	3	US
University of Florida	3	US
WA Museum	2	Australia
Mabunji Aboriginal Resource Association Incorporated	2	Australia
Scarp Archaeology	2	Australia
Aboriginal Affairs Victoria	2	Australia
Archaeological and Heritage Management Solutions Pty Ltd	2	Australia
Archae-Aus	2	Australia
Wallis Heritage Consulting	2	Australia
Big Island Research Pty Ltd.	2	Australia
Dunkeld Pastoral Co. Pty Ltd Theda Station	2	Australia
Ochre Imprints	2	Australia
Extent Heritage Pty Ltd	2	Australia
Big Island Research Pty Ltd	2	Australia
Artefact Heritage Pty Ltd	2	Australia
South Australian Native Title Association	2	Australia
Flinders and Howick Islands Aboriginal Corporation	2	Australia
Traditional Owner	2	Australia
Namunidjbuk Aboriginal Corporation	2	Australia
Triple-E Consultants	2	Australia
Murujuga Aboriginal Corporation	2	Australia
University of Victoria	2	Australia
Defence Science and Technology Group	2	Australia
Department of Environment and Science	2	Australia
Australian Catholic University	2	Australia
Federation University Australia	2	Australia
Faculty of Medicine, Nursing and Health Sciences	2	Australia
National Park Service	2	Australia
Universität Innsbruck	2	Austria
Universidade de São Paulo	2	Brazil
National Research Council Canada	2	Canada

The University of British Columbia	2	Canada
University of Guelph	2	Canada
Max-Planck-Institut für Evolutionäre Anthropologie	2	Germany
Universität Bonn	2	Germany
National Institute of Oceanography India	2	India
Pusat Penelitian Arkeologi Nasional	2	Indonesia
Massey University	2	New Zealand
Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	2	Russia
CSIC - Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales MNCN	2	Spain
Uppsala Universitet	2	Sweden
Université de Genève	2	Switzerland
Academia Sinica Taiwan	2	Taiwan
University of East Anglia	2	UK
National Oceanography Centre Southampton	2	UK
Florida State University	2	US
Princeton University	2	US
Arizona State University	2	US
Cornell University	2	US
California State University, Sacramento	2	US
University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	2	US
University of California, Davis	2	US
Colorado School of Mines	2	US
East Carolina University	2	US
San Diego State University	2	US
The Australian National University	134	Australia
The University of Western Australia	131	Australia
Flinders University	120	Australia
TOTAL AFFILIATION COUNTS	1696	

Table S5 Percentage of author affiliations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Africa. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL AFFILIATIONS
US	27.0
South Africa	16.1
UK	13.8
France	13.7
Germany	6.8
Australia	5.5
Spain	3.8
China	1.4
Norway	1.4
Portugal	1.2
Russia	1.2
Italy	1.1
Japan	0.9
Kenya	0.7
Netherlands	0.7
Canada	0.7
Israel	0.7
Nigeria	0.7
Sweden	0.6
Belgium	0.5
Ghana	0.5
Tanzania	0.4
Ethiopia	0.3
Indonesia	0.3

Table S6 Percentage of author affiliations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Asia. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL AFFILIATIONS
US	22.4
UK	16.5
Russia	12.1
Australia	11.7
China	10.1
France	6.6
Germany	5.3
Spain	2.1
Israel	1.3
Japan	1.1
Canada	1.0
Estonia	0.9
Belgium	0.8
Kazakhstan	0.8
Philippines	0.7
Denmark	0.7
Sweden	0.7
Singapore	0.7
Netherlands	0.5
South Africa	0.5
Korea	0.5
Uzbekistan	0.4
India	0.4
Taiwan	0.4
Armenia	0.3
Austria	0.3
Norway	0.3
Poland	0.3
Switzerland	0.3
Ukraine	0.3

Table S7 Percentage of author affiliations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Europe. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL AFFILIATIONS
UK	24.3
US	18.7
France	9.2
Russia	6.6
Spain	6.5
Germany	6.0
Netherlands	4.1
Australia	3.3
Italy	3.1
Poland	2.7
Israel	2.0
Denmark	1.4
Czech Republic	1.3
China	1.2
Sweden	1.0
Croatia	1.0
Canada	0.9
Norway	0.9
Belgium	0.7
Finland	0.7
Slovenia	0.7
Switzerland	0.5
Estonia	0.5
Portugal	0.5
Slovakia	0.4
South Africa	0.4
Ukraine	0.4
Greece	0.4
Hungry	0.4
Singapore	0.4

Table S8 Percentage of author affiliations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Australia. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL AFFILIATIONS
Australia	77.7
US	6.3
UK	6.2
New Zealand	2.8
France	2.6
Germany	0.9
Canada	0.6
Spain	0.6
Netherlands	0.5
South Africa	0.4
Israel	0.4
Argentina	0.2
Austria	0.1
Brazil	0.1
India	0.1
Indonesia	0.1
Russia	0.1
Sweden	0.1
Switzerland	0.1
Taiwan	0.1

Table S9 Africa Percentage of total author affiliations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Africa. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
South Africa	17.6
Nigeria	0.7
Ghana	0.5
Tanzania	0.4
Ethiopia	0.3
TOTAL	19.5
Asian Nations	
China	1.4
Japan*	0.9
Indonesia	0.3
Israel*	0.7
TOTAL	3.3
<i>Global South</i>	<i>1.7</i>
<i>Global North</i>	<i>1.6</i>
Australia	
TOTAL	5.5
European Nations	
UK	13.8
France	13.7
Germany	6.8
Spain	3.8
Norway	1.4
Portugal	1.2
Italy	1.1
Netherlands	0.7
Sweden	0.6
Belgium	0.5
TOTAL	43.7
North American Nations	
US	26.2
Canada	0.7
TOTAL	26.8
Russia	
TOTAL	1.2
South American Nations	
TOTAL	0

Table S10 Asia Percentage of total author affiliations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Asia. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
South Africa	0.5
TOTAL	0.5
Asian Nations	
China	10.1
India	0.4
Israel*	1.3
Japan*	1.1
Kazakhstan	0.8
Philippines	0.7
Singapore	0.7
South Korea*	0.5
Taiwan	0.4
Uzbekistan	0.4
TOTAL	16.4
<i>Global South</i>	13.5
<i>Global North*</i>	2.9
Australia	11.7
TOTAL	11.7
European Nations	
Armenia	0.3
Austria	0.3
Belgium	0.8
Denmark	0.7
Estonia	0.9
France	6.1
Germany	5.3
Netherlands	0.5
Norway	0.3
Poland	0.3
Spain	2.6
Sweden	0.7
Switzerland	0.3
UK	16.5
Ukraine	0.3
TOTAL	35.9
North American Nations	
Canada	1.0
US	22.4
TOTAL	23.4
Russia	12.1
South American Nations	0

Table S11 Europe Percentage of total author affiliations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Europe. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
South Africa	0.4
TOTAL	0.4
Asian Nations	
China	1.2
Israel*	2.0
Singapore	0.4
TOTAL	3.6
<i>Global South</i>	1.6
<i>Global North*</i>	2.0
Australia	
TOTAL	3.3
European Nations	
Belgium	0.7
Croatia	1.0
Czech Republic	1.3
Denmark	1.4
Estonia	0.5
Finland	0.7
France	9.2
Germany	6.0
Greece	0.4
Hungary	0.4
Italy	3.1
Netherlands	4.1
Norway	0.9
Poland	2.7
Portugal	0.5
Slovakia	0.4
Spain	7.2
Sweden	1.0
Switzerland	0.5
UK	24.3
Ukraine	0.4
TOTAL	66.5
North American Nations	
Canada	0.9
US	18.7
TOTAL	19.6
Russia	
TOTAL	6.6
South American Nations	0

Table S12 Australia Percentage of total author affiliations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Australia. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
South Africa	0.4
TOTAL	0.4
Asian Nations	
India	0.1
Indonesia	0.1
Israel	0.4
Taiwan	0.1
TOTAL	0.7
<i>Global South</i>	<i>0.4</i>
<i>Global North</i>	<i>0.4</i>
Australia & New Zealand	
Australia	77.7
New Zealand	2.8
TOTAL	80.5
European Nations	
France	2.6
Germany	0.9
Netherlands	0.5
Spain	0.6
Sweden	0.1
Switzerland	0.1
UK	6.2
TOTAL	11.0
North American Nations	
Canada	0.6
US	6.3
TOTAL	6.9
Russia	
TOTAL	0.1
South American Nations	
Argentina	0.2
Brazil	0.1
TOTAL	0.3

Funding data

Africa

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND evolution* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo*and AND dispersal* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND dispersal* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND fossil* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND fossil* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archaeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND africa*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND africa*)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART"))

Table S13 Funding bodies, institutions, and organisations listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Africa. Institutions ranked by count number. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

FUNDING SPONSOR	COUNT	COUNTRY
National Science Foundation	48	US
Leakey Foundation	25	US
National Research Foundation	24	South Africa
European Research Council	21	EU
Seventh Framework Programme	20	EU
University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg	19	South Africa
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	16	Germany
Wenner-Gren Foundation	16	US
Australian Research Council	15	Australia
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	12	France
National Geographic Society	11	US
Natural Environment Research Council	10	UK
University of Cape Town	10	South Africa
Max-Planck-Gesellschaft	9	Germany
National Natural Science Foundation of China	9	China
Agence Nationale de la Recherche	8	France
Heidelberger Akademie der Wissenschaften	8	Germany
Horizon 2020 Framework Programme	8	EU
National Institutes of Health	8	US
PAST	8	South Africa
Arts and Humanities Research Council	7	UK
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	7	Germany
European Commission	7	EU
Leverhulme Trust	7	Germany
National Research Foundation of Korea	7	Korea
Japan Society for the Promotion of Science	6	Japan
Ministère des Affaires Etrangères	6	Rwanda
National Institute of General Medical Sciences	6	US

Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada	6	Canada
Tanzania Commission for Science and Technology	6	Tanzania
Universitetet i Bergen	6	Norway
British Academy	5	UK
Directorate for Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences	5	US
Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación	5	Spain
Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad	5	Spain
Russian Foundation for Basic Research	5	Russia
Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung	4	Germany
Fondation Fyssen	4	France
Harvard University	4	US
Hyde Family Foundation	4	US
National Museum of Natural History	4	US
Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	4	Netherlands
University of Pennsylvania	4	US
Andrew W. Mellon Foundation	3	US
Arizona State University	3	US
Chinese Academy of Sciences	3	China
Economic and Social Research Council	3	UK
Fundação de Desenvolvimento da Pesquisa	3	Brazil
Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia	3	Portugal
Gerda Henkel Foundation	3	Germany
Israel Science Foundation	3	Israel
John Templeton Foundation	3	US
Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades	3	Spain
Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca	3	Italy
Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism	3	Tanzania
Royal Anthropological Institute	3	UK
University of California, Davis	3	US
University of Cambridge	3	UK
University of Dar es Salaam	3	Tanzania
University of Oxford	3	UK
Volkswagen Foundation	3	Germany
Agencia Estatal de Investigación	2	Spain
American Museum of Natural History	2	US
Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council	2	UK
Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico	2	Brazil
Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior	2	Brazil
Department of Antiquities	2	Cyprus
Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst France	2	Germany
European Science Foundation	2	EU
Fonds Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	2	Netherlands
Gonville and Caius College, University of Cambridge	2	UK
Horizon 2020	2	EU
Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan	2	Malaysia
La Trobe University	2	Australia
Liverpool John Moores University	2	UK
Ministère de la Culture	2	France
Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires Étrangères	2	France
Ministero degli Affari Esteri e della Cooperazione Internazionale	2	Italy
Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism	2	Italy
Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle	2	France
National Basic Research Program of China (973 Program)	2	China

National Eye Research Centre	2	US
National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute	2	US
Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada	2	Canada
Norges Forskningsråd	2	Norway
Royal Geographical Society	2	UK
Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung	2	Switzerland
Smithsonian Institution	2	US
Social Science Research Council	2	US
South African National Parks	2	South Africa
United States Agency for International Development	2	US
Universitat Rovira i Virgili	2	Spain
University of Connecticut	2	US
University of Johannesburg	2	South Africa
University of Western Australia	2	Australia
Aarhus Universitets Forskningsfond	1	Denmark
Addis Ababa University	1	Ethiopia
African Studies Association of the UK	1	UK
Agència de Gestió d'Ajuts Universitaris i de Recerca	1	Spain
All Souls College, University of Oxford	1	UK
American Council of Learned Societies	1	US
American Philosophical Society	1	US
Apex Foundation	1	UK
Australian Catholic University	1	Australia
Australian National University	1	Australia
Austrian Science Fund	1	Australia
AXA Research Fund	1	EU
Binghamton University	1	UK
Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung	1	Germany
Campus Research Board	1	UK
Canada Foundation for Innovation	1	Canada
Canada Research Chairs	1	Canada
Canadian Institute for Advanced Research	1	Canada
Canadian Institutes of Health Research	1	Canada
Case Western Reserve University	1	US
Center for Advanced Study, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign	1	US
Center for Information Technology	1	US
China Postdoctoral Science Foundation	1	China
College of Liberal Arts and Social Sciences, University of North Texas	1	US
Colleges and Universities in Hebei Province Science and Technology Research Project	1	China
Comisión Nacional de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica	1	Chile
Conseil Français de l'Énergie	1	France
Conseil Régional Aquitaine	1	France
Conseil Régional Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur	1	France
Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología	1	Mexico
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	1	Spain
Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, South Africa	1	South Africa
Department for International Development, UK Government	1	UK
Department of Anthropology, McMaster University	1	Canada
Department of Education and Training	1	Australia

Department of Science and Technology, Ministry of Science and Technology, India	1	India
Department of Science and Technology, Republic of South Africa	1	South Africa
Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst	1	Germany
Diabetes Institutes Foundation	1	US
DigitalGlobe Foundation	1	Switzerland
Dirección General de Asuntos del Personal Académico, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México	1	Mexico
DST-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology	1	South Africa
Ella ja Georg Ehrnroothin Säätiö	1	Finland
Ernest Oppenheimer Memorial Trust	1	South Africa
Ethicon	1	US
Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development	1	US
European Synchrotron Radiation Facility	1	EU
Explorers Club	1	US
Federación Española de Enfermedades Raras	1	Spain
Fédération pour la Recherche sur le Cerveau	1	France
Fondation des Treilles	1	France
Fondo Nacional de Desarrollo Científico y Tecnológico	1	Chile
Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian	1	Portugal
Fundação Carlos Chagas Filho de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro	1	Brazil
Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais	1	Brazil
Fundació Catalana de Trasplantament	1	Spain
Fundación Palarq	1	Spain
Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities	1	EU
Fundo Regional para a Ciência e Tecnologia	1	Brazil
FURTHERMORE grants in publishing	1	US
Government Council on Grants, Russian Federation	1	Russia
Grant Foundation	1	Australia
Grantová Agentura České Republiky	1	Czech Republic
H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	1	Poland
National Science Foundation	48	US
TOTAL FUNDING INSTITUTIONS	615	

Asia

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND evolution* AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND dispersal AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND fossil* AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hominin AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hominid AND asia*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND asia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND asia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human AND dispersal AND asia)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART")))

Table S14 Funding bodies, institutions, and organisations listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Asia. Institutions ranked by count number. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

FUNDING SPONSOR	COUNT	COUNTRY
National Science Foundation	80	US
National Natural Science Foundation of China	58	China
Australian Research Council	50	Australia
Chinese Academy of Sciences	37	China
European Research Council	33	EU
Russian Foundation for Basic Research	32	US
Wenner-Gren Foundation	31	US
National Geographic Society	28	US
Horizon 2020 Framework Programme	25	EU
Japan Society for the Promotion of Science	25	Japan
Russian Science Foundation	25	Russia
Max-Planck-Gesellschaft	20	Germany
Seventh Framework Programme	19	EU
Arts and Humanities Research Council	19	UK
Natural Environment Research Council	19	UK
National Institutes of Health	19	US
Leakey Foundation	17	US
Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada	16	Canada
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	16	Germany
National Institute of General Medical Sciences	16	US
European Commission	14	EU
Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology	14	Japan
National Key Research and Development Program of China	11	China
Leverhulme Trust	11	Germany
Russian Academy of Sciences	11	Russia
British Academy	11	UK
Agence Nationale de la Recherche	10	France
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	10	France
Wellcome Trust	10	UK
National Human Genome Research Institute	10	US
China Scholarship Council	8	China
Ministry of Science and Technology of the People's Republic of China	8	China
National Office for Philosophy and Social Sciences	8	China

Horizon 2020	8	EU
University of Cambridge	8	UK
Israel Science Foundation	7	Israel
Howard Hughes Medical Institute	7	US
European Regional Development Fund	6	EU
Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities	6	EU
Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council	6	UK
American Philosophical Society	6	US
John Templeton Foundation	6	US
University of Chicago	6	US
Griffith University	5	Australia
Austrian Science Fund	5	Austria
European Social Fund	5	EU
Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle	5	France
Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan	5	Kazakhstan
National Research Foundation of Korea	5	Korea
Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation	5	Russia
Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad	5	Spain
Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung	5	Switzerland
Harvard University	5	UK
Institute of Archaeology, University College London	5	UK
American Institute of Indian Studies	5	US
Henry Luce Foundation	5	US
National Eye Research Centre	5	US
University of Wollongong	4	Australia
Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada	4	Canada
China Postdoctoral Science Foundation	4	China
Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China	4	China
National Basic Research Program of China (973 Program)	4	China
Gerda Henkel Foundation	4	Germany
Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	4	Russia
Ministère des Affaires Etrangères	4	Rwanda
Arts and Humanities Research Board	4	UK
Royal Society	4	UK
National Museum of Natural History	4	US
Smithsonian Institution	4	US
U.S. Geological Survey	4	US
Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología	3	Argentina
Australian Institute of Nuclear Science and Engineering	3	Australia
Australian National University	3	Australia
Department of Education and Training	3	Australia
Ministry for Foreign Affairs	3	Australia
Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism	3	Australia
Ministry of Education	3	Australia
National Science Council	3	Australia
University of Queensland	3	Australia
Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico	3	Brazil
Academia Sinica	3	China
Zhengzhou University	3	China
Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung	3	Germany
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	3	Germany
Institute for Aegean Prehistory	3	Greece

Irish Research Council	3	Ireland
Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	3	Netherlands
University of the Philippines	3	Philippines
Narodowe Centrum Nauki	3	Poland
Narodowym Centrum Nauki	3	Poland
Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia	3	Portugal
Government Council on Grants, Russian Federation	3	Russia
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	3	Spain
Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte	3	Spain
Universitat Rovira i Virgili	3	Spain
Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung	3	Switzerland
Thailand Research Fund	3	Thailand
University College London	3	UK
American Council of Learned Societies	3	US
American Research Institute in Turkey	3	US
National Aeronautics and Space Administration	3	US
National Cancer Institute	3	US
Stanford University	3	US
University of Arizona	3	US
University of New England	3	US
Waitt Family Foundation	3	US
National Academy of Sciences of Armenia	2	Armenia
Flinders University	2	Australia
International Business Machines Corporation	2	Australia
Ministry of Finance	2	Australia
Monash University	2	Australia
Fonds de Recherche du Québec-Société et Culture	2	Canada
McGill University	2	Canada
Higher Education Discipline Innovation Project	2	China
Nanjing University	2	China
Danmarks Frie Forskningsfond	2	Denmark
Eesti Teadusagentuur	2	Estonia
Haridus- ja Teadusministeerium	2	Estonia
Academy of Finland	2	Finland
Fondation Fyssen	2	France
Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires Étrangères	2	France
Max-Planck-Institut für Evolutionäre Anthropologie	2	Germany
Max-Planck-Institut für Menschheitsgeschichte	2	Germany
Magyar Tudományos Akadémia	2	Hungary
Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, India	2	India
Department of Science and Technology, Ministry of Science and Technology, India	2	India
Indian Council of Historical Research	2	India
Bar-Ilan University	2	Israel
Lietuvos Mokslo Taryba	2	Lithuania
Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan	2	Malaysia
Dirección General de Asuntos del Personal Académico, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México	2	Mexico
Fonds Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	2	Netherlands
Lundbeckfonden	2	Netherlands
American Institute of Pakistan Studies	2	Pakistan

Javna Agencija za Raziskovalno Dejavnost RS	2	Slovenia
Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación	2	Spain
DigitalGlobe Foundation	2	Switzerland
Ministry of Science and Technology, Taiwan	2	Taiwan
Istanbul Üniversitesi	2	Turkey
Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council	2	UK
Isaac Newton Trust	2	UK
Marie Curie	2	UK
Medical Research Council	2	UK
Albion College	2	US
American Academy of Religion	2	US
American Research Institute of the South Caucasus	2	US
Andrew W. Mellon Foundation	2	US
Baylor University	2	US
Broad Institute	2	US
Brown University	2	US
Cornell University	2	US
Council of American Overseas Research Centers	2	US
Directorate for Social, Behavioral and Economic Sciences	2	US
Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection	2	US
Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development	2	US
Florida Museum of Natural History	2	US
Ford Foundation	2	US
Fulbright Association	2	US
National Endowment for the Humanities	2	US
National Science Foundation	80	US
TOTAL FUNDING INSTITUTIONS	1123	

Europe

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND evolution* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo*and AND dispersal* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND dispersal* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND fossil* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND fossil* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archaeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND archaeology* AND europe*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND europe*)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART"))

Table S15 Funding bodies, institutions, and organisations listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Europe. Institutions ranked by count number. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>)..

FUNDING SPONSOR	COUNT	COUNTRY
European Commission	28	EU
European Research Council	26	EU
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	25	Germany
Horizon 2020 Framework Programme	24	UK
Seventh Framework Programme	21	EU
National Science Foundation	20	US
Russian Science Foundation	16	Russia
Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación	16	Spain
European Regional Development Fund	14	EU
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	12	Germany
Russian Foundation for Basic Research	12	Russia
Leverhulme Trust	12	UK
Natural Environment Research Council	11	UK
Leakey Foundation	11	US
Max-Planck-Gesellschaft	10	Germany
Agence Nationale de la Recherche	9	France
Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	9	Netherlands
Generalitat de Catalunya	9	Spain
National Institutes of Health	9	US
National Natural Science Foundation of China	8	China
Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation	8	Russia
Arts and Humanities Research Council	8	UK
Wenner-Gren Foundation	8	US
Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada	7	Canada
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	7	France
Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad	7	Spain
Wellcome Trust	7	UK
Australian Research Council	6	Australia
Grantová Agentura České Republiky	6	Czech Republic
Horizon 2020	6	EU

Norges Forskningsråd	6	Norway
Narodowe Centrum Nauki	6	Poland
Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades	6	Spain
National Human Genome Research Institute	6	US
National Institute of General Medical Sciences	6	US
Akademie Věd České Republiky	5	Czech Republic
Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung	5	Germany
Università degli Studi di Ferrara	5	Italy
Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia	5	Portugal
British Academy	5	UK
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	4	Argentina
Austrian Science Fund	4	Austria
Chinese Academy of Sciences	4	China
Danmarks Grundforskningsfond	4	Denmark
Academy of Finland	4	Finland
Ministère de la Culture	4	France
Israel Science Foundation	4	Israel
H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	4	Poland
Vedecká Grantová Agentúra MŠVVaŠ SR a SAV	4	Slovakia
Agència de Gestió d'Ajuts Universitaris i de Recerca	4	Spain
Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung	4	Switzerland
National Geographic Society	4	US
University of Western Australia	3	Australia
Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften	3	Austria
Ministarstvo Prosvete, Nauke i Tehnološkog Razvoja	3	Bosnia
Canada Foundation for Innovation	3	Canada
Eesti Teadusagentuur	3	Estonia
Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca	3	Italy
Narodowym Centrum Nauki	3	Poland
Government Council on Grants, Russian Federation	3	Russia
Russian Academy of Sciences	3	Russia
Agencia Estatal de Investigación	3	Spain
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	3	Spain
Universidad de Cantabria	3	Spain
Universitat Rovira i Virgili	3	Spain
Economic and Social Research Council	3	UK
Royal Society	3	UK
National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute	3	US
University of Arizona	3	US
Agencia Nacional de Promoción Científica y Tecnológica	2	Argentina
Fondo para la Investigación Científica y Tecnológica	2	Argentina
Australian Catholic University	2	Australia
Australian National University	2	Australia
Griffith University	2	Australia
University of Adelaide	2	Australia
Medizinische Universität Innsbruck	2	Austria
KU Leuven	2	Belgium
Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo	2	Brazil
National Office for Philosophy and Social Sciences	2	China
Carlsbergfondet	2	Denmark
Institut National Du Cancer	2	Denmark

Københavns Universitet	2	Denmark
Lundbeckfonden	2	Denmark
Natur og Univers, Det Frie Forskningsråd	2	Denmark
Novo Nordisk Fonden	2	Denmark
Haridus- ja Teadusministeerium	2	Estonia
European Science Foundation	2	EU
European Social Fund	2	EU
H2020 European Research Council	2	EU
Sixth Framework Programme	2	EU
Fondation Fyssen	2	France
Fondation de France	2	France
Fondation du Collège de France	2	France
Ministère de la Culture et de la Communication	2	France
Université de Bordeaux	2	France
Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung	2	Germany
Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst	2	Germany
Gerda Henkel Foundation	2	Germany
Heidelberger Akademie der Wissenschaften	2	Germany
Ministerium für Wissenschaft, Forschung und Kunst Baden-Württemberg	2	Germany
Universität Hamburg	2	Germany
Volkswagen Foundation	2	Germany
Indian Council of Agricultural Research	2	India
Heritage Council	2	Ireland
Hebrew University of Jerusalem	2	Israel
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	2	Italy
Kazan Federal University	2	Russia
Siberian Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	2	Russia
Ural Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences	2	Russia
Deanship of Scientific Research, King Saud University	2	Saudi Arabia
Slovenská Akadémia Vied	2	Slovakia
Federación Española de Enfermedades Raras	2	Spain
Fundació Catalana de Trasplantament	2	Spain
Fundación Séneca	2	Spain
Junta de Andalucía	2	Spain
Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte	2	Spain
Universidad Complutense de Madrid	2	Spain
Uppsala Universitet	2	Sweden
Vetenskapsrådet	2	Sweden
Roche	2	Switzerland
Université de Genève	2	Switzerland
Ministry of Science and Technology, Taiwan	2	Taiwan
Cancer Research UK	2	UK
Deakin University	2	UK
Medical Research Council	2	UK
National Eye Research Centre	2	UK
UK Research and Innovation	2	UK
University of Cambridge	2	UK
Andrew W. Mellon Foundation	2	US
Case Western Reserve University	2	US
Columbia University	2	US
Corporation for National and Community Service	2	US

Howard Hughes Medical Institute	2	US
National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences	2	US
National Endowment for the Humanities	2	US
Waitt Family Foundation	2	US
Australian Renewable Energy Agency	1	Australia
British Columbia Knowledge Development Fund	1	Canada
A.G. Leventis Foundation	1	Cyprus
Agence de l'Eau Rhône Méditerranée Corse	1	France
Aix-Marseille Université	1	France
Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung	1	Germany
BASF	1	Germany
Aard- en Levenswetenschappen, Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	1	Netherlands
Academia Româna	1	Romania
Agentúra na Podporu Výskumu a Vývoja	1	Slovakia
Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council	1	UK
Bournemouth University	1	UK
British Archaeological Association	1	UK
AFCEA Educational Foundation	1	US
American Academy of Religion	1	US
American Association of Geographers	1	US
American Association of University Women	1	US
American Institute of Indian Studies	1	US
American Institute of Pakistan Studies	1	US
American Museum of Natural History	1	US
American-Scandinavian Foundation	1	US
Arizona State University	1	US
Biogen	1	US
European Commission	28	EU
TOTAL FUNDING INSTITUTIONS	683	

Australia

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND dispersal AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND dispersal AND sahum)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART"))

Table S16 Funding bodies, institutions, and organisations listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Australia. Institutions ranked by count number. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

FUNDING SPONSOR	COUNT	COUNTRY
Australian Research Council	213	Australia
La Trobe University	18	Australia
Flinders University	17	Australia
Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies	16	Australia
University of Western Australia	16	Australia
Department of Education and Training	14	Australia
Monash University	12	Australia
Australian Government	11	Australia
Australian Institute of Nuclear Science and Engineering	11	Australia
University of Sydney	11	Australia
University of Melbourne	10	Australia
National Science Foundation	10	US
Kimberley Foundation Australia	9	Australia
University of Auckland	8	New Zealand
Macquarie University	7	Australia
University of Queensland	6	Australia
Australian Museum	5	Australia
Australian National University	5	Australia
British Columbia Knowledge Development Fund	5	Canada
Canada Foundation for Innovation	5	Canada
Canada Research Chairs	5	Canada
Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada	5	Canada
Association pour la Recherche sur le Cancer	5	France
Wenner-Gren Foundation	5	US
European Research Council	4	Europe
Curtin University of Technology	3	Australia
National Parks and Wildlife Service	3	Australia
University of Adelaide	3	Australia
University of New England	3	Australia
University of New South Wales	3	Australia
University of Wollongong	3	Australia
Horizon 2020 Framework Programme	3	Europe
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	3	Germany

Heritage New Zealand Pouhere Taonga	3	New Zealand
Marsden Fund	3	New Zealand
British Academy	3	UK
Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation	3	UK
Harvard University	3	US
BHP	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Coherent X-Ray Science, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Coral Reef Studies, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Core to Crust Fluid Systems, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Electromaterials Science, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Environmental Decisions, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Integrative Brain Function, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Particle Physics at the Terascale, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence in Cognition and its Disorders, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence in Future Low-Energy Electronics Technologies, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Centre of Excellence in Plant Energy Biology, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
Charles Darwin University	2	Australia
Commonwealth Scholarship Commission	2	Australia
Department of Sustainability and Environment	2	Australia
Government of Western Australia	2	Australia
Griffith University	2	Australia
James Cook University	2	Australia
Training Centre for Food and Beverage Supply Chain Optimisation, Australian Research Council	2	Australia
University of Technology Sydney	2	Australia
Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico	2	Brazil
Simon Fraser University	2	Canada
Seventh Framework Programme	2	Europe
Max-Planck-Gesellschaft	2	Germany
Japan Society for the Promotion of Science	2	Japan
Royal Society of New Zealand	2	New Zealand
Arts and Humanities Research Council	2	UK
Appalachian Regional Commission	2	US
National Geographic Society	2	US
Texas State University	2	US
U.S. Department of Energy	2	US
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	1	Argentina
Arts Victoria	1	Australia
Asthma Foundation of Western Australia	1	Australia
Australian Academy of the Humanities	1	Australia

Australian Agency for International Development	1	Australia
Australian Geographic Society	1	Australia
Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation	1	Australia
Australian Research Council Centre of Excellence in Advanced Molecular Imaging	1	Australia
Australian Respiratory Council	1	Australia
Austrian Science Fund	1	Australia
Centre of Excellence for Quantum Computation and Communication Technology, Australian Research Council	1	Australia
Chevron Australia	1	Australia
Cooperative Research Centres, Australian Government Department of Industry	1	Australia
DST-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology	1	Australia
Deakin University	1	Australia
Defence Science and Technology Group	1	Australia
Department of Environment and Science, Queensland Government	1	Australia
Department of Environment, Water and Natural Resources	1	Australia
Department of Health, Australian Government	1	Australia
Department of the Environment, Australian Government	1	Australia
Environmental Futures Research Institute, Griffith University	1	Australia
Forrest Research Foundation	1	Australia
Griffith Asia Institute, Griffith University	1	Australia
Griffith Criminology Institute, Griffith University	1	Australia
Griffith Health Institute, Griffith University	1	Australia
Griffith Institute for Tourism, Griffith University	1	Australia
Ian Potter Foundation	1	Australia
Linnean Society of NSW	1	Australia
Murdoch University	1	Australia
NSW Department of Education	1	Australia
NSW Office of Environment and Heritage	1	Australia
National Drug Research Institute	1	Australia
National Health and Medical Research Council	1	Australia
National Measurement Institute	1	Australia
National Stroke Foundation	1	Australia
Natural Environment Research Council	1	Australia
New South Wales Government	1	Australia
Northern Territory Government	1	Australia
Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos	1	Brazil
Fundação Carlos Chagas Filho de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro	1	Brazil
National Research Council Canada	1	Canada
Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada	1	Canada
European Commission	1	Europe
European Science Foundation	1	Europe
Honor Frost Foundation	1	Europe
Horizon 2020	1	Europe
Marie Curie	1	Europe
Agence Nationale de la Recherche	1	France
Fondation Aix-Marseille Université	1	France
Institut Universitaire de France	1	France
National Council for Scientific Research	1	France
Max-Planck-Institut für Evolutionäre Anthropologie	1	Germany

Munich-Centre for Advanced Photonics	1	Germany
Ministry of Education, India	1	India
Irish Research Council for the Humanities and Social Sciences	1	Ireland
Instituto de Ecología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México	1	Mexico
Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	1	Netherlands
Allan Wilson Centre	1	New Zealand
Norges Forskningsråd	1	Norway
Ministry of Education - Singapore	1	Singapore
National Research Foundation Singapore	1	Singapore
Myndigheten för Samhällsskydd och Beredskap	1	Sweden
Myndigheten för Samhällsskydd och Beredskap	1	Sweden
Asia University	1	Taiwan
BHP Billiton	1	UK
Calleva Foundation	1	UK
City, University of London	1	UK
Clare College, University of Cambridge	1	UK
Higher Education Funding Council for England	1	UK
Homerton College, University of Cambridge	1	UK
Leverhulme Trust	1	UK
National Lottery Heritage Fund	1	UK
Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine	1	Ukraine
American Anthropological Association	1	US
American Architectural Foundation	1	US
American Association for Anatomy	1	US
American Speech-Language-Hearing Association	1	US
Arizona State University	1	US
Camille and Henry Dreyfus Foundation	1	US
East Carolina University	1	US
Eastman Kodak	1	US
Kansas Department of Wildlife and Parks	1	US
Kansas Historical Society	1	US
Leakey Foundation	1	US
Medical College of Wisconsin	1	US
National Centre for Supercomputing Applications	1	US
National Institute of Dental and Craniofacial Research	1	US
National Institute of General Medical Sciences	1	US
National Institutes of Health	1	US
National Nuclear Security Administration	1	US
Office of Naval Research	1	US
TOTAL FUNDING INSTITUTIONS	623	

Table S17 Percentage of funding bodies, institutions, and organisations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Africa. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL FUNDING SPONSORS
US	28.0
South Africa	11.2
EU	10.2
Germany	9.9
UK	7.8
France	5.7
Australia	3.9
Spain	3.6
China	2.6
Canada	2.1
Tanzania	2.0
Brazil	1.6
Norway	1.3
Italy	1.1
Korea	1.1
Russia	1.0
Japan	1.0
Netherlands	1.0
Rwanda	1.0
Portugal	0.7
Israel	0.5
Switzerland	0.5
Chile	0.3
Cyprus	0.3
Malaysia	0.3
Mexico	0.3
Czech Republic	0.2
Denmark	0.2
Ethiopia	0.2
Finland	0.2
India	0.2
Poland	0.2

Table S18 Percentage of funding bodies, institutions, and organisations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Asia. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL FUNDING SPONSORS
US	30.4
China	13.5
EU	10.3
UK	9.1
Australia	8.1
Germany	5.4
Russia	4.3
Japan	3.5
France	2.6
Canada	2.1
Spain	1.4
Switzerland	0.9
Israel	0.8
Netherlands	0.6
India	0.5
Poland	0.5
Austria	0.4
Kazakhstan	0.4
Korea	0.4
Estonia	0.4
Rwanda	0.4
Philippines	0.3
Argentina	0.3
Brazil	0.3
Greece	0.3
Ireland	0.3
Portugal	0.3
Thailand	0.3
Armenia	0.2
Denmark	0.2
Finland	0.2
Hungry	0.2
Lithuania	0.2
Malaysia	0.2
Mexico	0.2
Pakistan	0.2
Slovenia	0.2
Taiwan	0.2
Turkey	0.2

Table S19 Percentage of funding bodies, institutions, and organisations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Europe. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL FUNDING SPONSORS
EU	15.1
US	14.1
UK	12.9
Germany	10.0
Spain	9.7
Russia	7.0
France	4.7
Australia	2.6
Denmark	2.3
China	2.0
Poland	1.9
Czech Republic	1.6
Canada	1.6
Netherlands	1.5
Italy	1.5
Austria	1.3
Switzerland	1.2
Argentina	1.2
Slovakia	1.0
Norway	0.9
Israel	0.9
Estonia	0.7
Portugal	0.7
Finland	0.6
Sweden	0.6
Bosnia	0.4
Belgium	0.3
Ireland	0.3
Brazil	0.3
India	0.3
Taiwan	0.3
Saudi Arabia	0.3
Cyprus	0.1
Romania	0.1

Table S20 Percentage of funding bodies, institutions, and organisations per country listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Australia. Countries are ranked by total affiliation percentage. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

COUNTRY	% TOTAL FUNDING SPONSORS
Australia	76.1
US	7.1
Canada	3.9
New Zealand	2.7
UK	2.6
Europe	2.2
France	1.4
Germany	1.1
Brazil	0.6
Japan	0.3
Singapore	0.3
Sweden	0.3
Argentina	0.2
India	0.2
Ireland	0.2
Mexico	0.2
Netherlands	0.2
Norway	0.2
Taiwan	0.2
Ukraine	0.2

Table S22 Africa Percentage of total funding bodies, institutions, and organisations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Africa. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
Ethiopia	0.2
Rwanda	1.0
South Africa	11.2
Tanzania	2.0
TOTAL	14.3
Asian Nations	
China	2.6
India	0.2
Israel*	0.5
Japan*	1.0
South Korea*	1.1
TOTAL	5.7
<i>Global South</i>	3.1
<i>Global North*</i>	2.6
Australia	
TOTAL	3.9
European Nations	
Cyprus	0.3
Czech Republic	0.2
Denmark	0.2
EU	10.2
Finland	0.2
France	5.7
Germany	9.9
Italy	1.1
Netherlands	1.0
Norway	1.3
Poland	0.2
Portugal	0.7
Spain	3.6
Switzerland	0.5
UK	7.8
TOTAL	42.8
North American Nations	
Canada	2.1
US	28.0
TOTAL	30.1
Russia	
TOTAL	1.0
South American Nations	
Brazil	1.6

Chile	0.3
Mexico	0.3
TOTAL	2.3

Table S23 Asia Percentage of total funding bodies, institutions, and organisations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Asia. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
Rwanda	0.4
TOTAL	0.4
Asian Nations	
China	13.5
India	0.5
Israel	0.8
Japan	3.5
Kazakhstan	0.4
Korea	0.4
Malaysia	0.2
Pakistan	0.2
Philippines	0.3
Taiwan	0.2
Thailand	0.3
Turkey	0.2
TOTAL	20.5
European Nations	
Armenia	0.2
Austria	0.4
Denmark	0.2
Estonia	0.4
EU	10.3
Finland	0.2
France	2.6
Germany	5.4
Greece	0.3
Hungry	0.2
Ireland	0.3
Lithuania	0.2
Netherlands	0.6
Poland	0.5
Portugal	0.3
Slovenia	0.2
Spain	1.4
Switzerland	0.9
UK	9.1
TOTAL	33.6
North American Nations	
Canada	2.1
US	30.4
TOTAL	32.5

Russia	
TOTAL	4.3
South American Nations	
Argentina	0.3
Brazil	0.3
Mexico	0.2
TOTAL	0.7

Table S24 Europe Percentage of total funding bodies, institutions, and organisations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Europe. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
TOTAL	0
Asian Nations	
Saudi Arabia	0.3
China	2.0
India	0.3
Taiwan	0.3
Israel*	0.9
TOTAL	3.8
<i>Global South</i>	<i>2.9</i>
<i>Global North*</i>	<i>0.9</i>
European Nations	
Austria	1.3
Belgium	0.3
Bosnia	0.4
Cyprus	0.1
Czech Republic	1.6
Denmark	2.3
Estonia	0.7
EU	15.1
Finland	0.6
France	4.7
Germany	10.0
Ireland	0.3
Italy	1.5
Netherlands	1.5
Norway	0.9
Poland	1.9
Portugal	0.7
Romania	0.1
Slovakia	1.0
Spain	9.7
Sweden	0.6
Switzerland	1.2
UK	12.9
TOTAL	69.4
North American Nations	
Canada	1.6
US	14.1
TOTAL	15.7
Russia	
TOTAL	7.0

South American Nations	
Argentina	1.2
Brazil	0.3
TOTAL	1.5

Table S25 Australia Percentage of total funding bodies, institutions, and organisations for African, Asian, Australian, European, North American, Russian, and South American nations on publications focusing on human origins research in and on Australia. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>).

REGION/COUNTRY	%
African Nations	
TOTAL	0
Asian Nations	
India	0.2
Japan*	0.3
Singapore	0.3
Taiwan	0.2
TOTAL	1.0
<i>Global South</i>	<i>0.6</i>
<i>Global North</i>	<i>0.3</i>
European Nations	
EU	2.2
France	1.4
Germany	1.1
Ireland	0.2
Netherlands	0.2
Norway	0.2
Sweden	0.3
UK	2.6
Ukraine	0.2
TOTAL	8.3
North American Nations	
Canada	3.9
US	7.1
TOTAL	10.9
Russia	
TOTAL	0
South American Nations	
Argentina	0.2
Brazil	0.6
Mexico	0.2
TOTAL	1.0

ROAD

Table S26 Percentage of total human origin sites per country and geographic region (Africa, Asia, Europe, Russia). Data were obtained from the ROCEEH Out of Africa Database(ref) (ROAD, <http://www.roceeh.net>). Database accessed on 05/03/2024. The full list of spatial coordinates can be found in *Supplementary Information 2 – ROAD coordinates*.

Africa	
Algeria	0.5
Angola	0.2
Botswana	0.2
Cameroon	0.1
Congo, Democratic Republic of the [Zaire]	0.2
Congo, Republic of the	0.1
Djibouti	0.6
Egypt	1.1
Equatorial Guinea	0.1
Eritrea	0.2
Eswatini	0.1
Ethiopia	2.4
Gabon	0.1
Ghana	0.1
Kenya	3.8
Lesotho	0.3
Libya	0.6
Lithuania	0.1
Malawi	0.4
Mauritania	0.1
Morocco	1.3
Mozambique	0.2
Namibia	0.9
Niger	0.1
Senegal	0.1
Somalia	0.1
South Africa	8.1
Sudan	0.2
Tanzania	3.0
Tunisia	0.3
Yemen	0.2
Zambia	0.7
Zimbabwe	0.3
TOTAL	26.1
Asia	
Afghanistan	0.1
Armenia	2.7
Azerbaijan	0.1

Cambodia	0.2
China	5.4
India	1.4
Indonesia	5.1
Iran	0.7
Iraq	0.2
Israel	2.6
Japan	0.2
Jordan	0.4
Kazakhstan	0.4
Korea, North	0.3
Korea, South	0.4
Kyrgyzstan	0.1
Laos	0.3
Lebanon	0.1
Malaysia	0.4
Mongolia	0.6
Myanmar [Burma]	0.1
Oman	0.1
Pakistan	0.1
Philippines	0.4
Saudi Arabia	0.4
Sri Lanka	0.1
Syria	0.5
Taiwan	0.1
Tajikistan	0.2
Thailand	0.6
Timor-Leste	0.1
Turkey	0.5
United Arab Emirates	0.1
Uzbekistan	0.3
Vietnam	1.0
West Bank	0.1
TOTAL	25.6
Europe	
Albania	0.1
Austria	1.0
Belarus	0.2
Belgium	0.7
Bosnia and Herzegovina	0.1
Bulgaria	0.2
Ceuta	0.1
Croatia	0.4
Czech Republic	0.7
Denmark	0.1

Estonia	0.1
Finland	0.1
France	14.4
Georgia	2.4
Germany	5.7
Gibraltar	0.1
Greece	0.8
Hungary	0.3
Italy	5.9
Jersey	0.1
Latvia	0.1
Moldova	0.1
Montenegro	0.2
Netherlands	0.3
North Macedonia	0.1
Norway	0.1
Poland	1.7
Portugal	1.8
Romania	0.5
Serbia	0.3
Slovakia	0.5
Slovenia	0.2
Spain	2.4
Sweden	0.1
Switzerland	0.3
United Kingdom	1.0
Ukraine	0.9
TOTAL	43.1
Russia	
Asian sites	2.5
European Sites	2.6
TOTAL	5.2

SahulArch

Table S27 Sahul (Australia and New Guinea) human origin sites included in the study. Shapefiles were obtained from the OCTOPUS database (v.2) OSL and Radiocarbon collections. Sites with occupation ages less than c. 20 ka were excluded to align with the ROAD dataset. Shapefiles can be obtained at <https://octopusdata.org/>.

Shapefile *	SITENAME
Point	21 Hassall Street
Point	2-8 River Road West
Point	330 Church Street
Point	Airport Mound
Point	Allen's Cave
Point	Angkitkita
Point	Bald Rock 1
Point	Beeton Rockshelter
Point	Beginners Luck Cave
Point	Bells Grove
Point	Bend Road
Point	Birrigai Rockshelter
Point	Bone Cave
Point	Boodie Cave
Point	Borologa 1
Point	Box Gully
Point	Buang Merabak
Point	Burrill Lake Rockshelter
Point	C99
Point	Carpenter's Gap 1
Point	Carpenter's Gap 3
Point	Cave Bay Cave
Point	Cheshunt Dune
Point	Classic Site
Point	Cloggs Cave
Point	Cluster 16
Point	Cluster 40
Point	Cluster 51
Point	Cluster 53
Point	Cluster 94
Point	Cluster 97
Point	Cluster RC11
Point	Cluster RC26
Point	COO13-43
Point	COO13-45
Point	COO13-47
Point	Cranebrook Terrace
Point	Cuddie Springs
Point	Cumberland Hospital
Point	Devil's Lair
Point	Djadjiling Rockshelter
Point	Druai
Point	Eliva Hamlet
Point	Fern Cave
Point	FP80

Point	FSHP Stage A Site
Point	Fundum
Point	Georges Street Gatehouse
Point	Gledswood Shelter 1
Point	Gnatalia Creek 1
Point	Green Gully
Point	Gregory River 8
Point	H366
Point	Hay Cave
Point	Hearth Cave
Point	Here Sorot Entapa
Point	Hope 1-41
Point	HS-A1
Point	Jansz
Point	Jinmium
Point	Joe's Garden
Point	JSARN-113/23
Point	Jundaru Rockshelter
Point	Juukan-1
Point	Juukan-2
Point	Kakutungutanta
Point	Kariyarra Rockshelter
Point	Karnatukul
Point	Karolta 1
Point	Katampul Rockshelter
Point	Keilor
Point	Kilu
Point	King's Tableland
Point	Koo Wee Rup
Point	Koolan Shelter 2
Point	Koonalda Cave
Point	Kosipe
Point	Kosipe Mission
Point	Kow Swamp
Point	Kulpi Mara
Point	Kupona na Dari
Point	Lachitu
Point	Lake Garnpung
Point	Lake Leaghur
Point	Lake Menindee
Point	Lake Mulurulu
Point	Lake Nitchie
Point	Lake Tandou
Point	Lake Woods 1
Point	Lake Yantara
Point	Laurie Creek
Point	Leaghur Channel
Point	Mackintosh 90/1
Point	Madjedbebe
Point	Malangangerr
Point	Malarrak 1
Point	Mandu Mandu Creek Rockshelter
Point	Mannalargenna Cave

Point	Matenbek
Point	Matenkupkum
Point	Mayne Site
Point	Mesa J24
Point	MIN14-03
Point	Minjigina
Point	Minjiwarra
Point	Monak Murray River
Point	Moyjil
Point	Mungo Lakebed
Point	Murubun Shelter
Point	Nauwalabila I
Point	Nawamoyrn
Point	Nawarla Gabarnmang
Point	New Guinea II Cave
Point	Newman Orebody XXIX
Point	Newman Rockshelter
Point	Ngarrabullgan Cave
Point	Noala Cave
Point	Nombe
Point	Nonda Rock
Point	Nunamira Cave
Point	OB24-2004/13
Point	OB24-FS4
Point	O'Connell Street Public School
Point	ODX-10478
Point	ODX-15546
Point	OGC 1
Point	ORS 7
Point	Outer Arumpo Lunette
Point	P0187
Point	P2055.2
Point	PACD H1
Point	PAD10-17
Point	Palais Royale
Point	Pallawa Trounta
Point	Panaramittee North
Point	Parawee Quarry
Point	Parmerpar Meethaner
Point	Peery Lake Hearths
Point	PikeAWE15_10
Point	PIL_3160
Point	PIL_364
Point	PIL_365
Point	PIL_3698
Point	PIL_4544
Point	Pilgonaman Creek Rockshelter
Point	Prungle Lakes
Point	PT 12
Point	Puritjarra
Point	RH12-01
Point	Riwi
Point	RS10-01

Point	RS10-03
Point	RTA-G1
Point	Sandy Creek 1
Point	Sandy Creek 2
Point	SGCD 16
Point	Silver Dollar Midden
Point	South Kov
Point	Tol Cave
Point	Tunnel Cave
Point	Upper Swan
Point	Vilakuav
Point	Walkunder Arch Cave
Point	Wallen Wallen Creek
Point	Wangangarra 1
Point	Warkworth Sand Sheet
Point	Warrananga
Point	Warreen Cave
Point	Watura Jurnti
Point	Wharton Hill
Point	Widgingarri Shelter 1
Point	WOC
Point	WOC-1
Point	WOC-149
Point	WOC-151
Point	WOC-2
Point	WOC-3
Point	WOC-4
Point	WOC-7
Point	Wollingurry Point
Point	Wyrie Swamp
Point	Yalibirri Mindi Rockshelter
Point	Yellabidde Cave
Point	Yombon Airstrip
Point	Yurlu Kankala

Tanzanian Case Study: Affiliation data

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND homo*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND hominin*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND homo AND sapiens) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND modern AND human*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND evolution* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND homo* AND dispersal*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND homo AND sapiens* AND dispersal*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND modern AND human* AND dispersal*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND hominin* AND dispersal*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND fossil* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hominin AND fossil* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND fossil* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND fossil* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(modern AND human* AND archaeology* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hominin* AND archaeology* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens* AND archaeology* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(hominin* AND archeology* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens* AND archeology* AND tanzania) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND middle AND stone AND age) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(tanzania AND early AND stone AND age)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART"))

Table S28 Percentage of Tanzanian, other African nations, and international author affiliations listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Tanzania from 1970 to 2024. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>). The full list of affiliations can be found in *Supplementary Information 3 – Case Study Affiliation Data*.

Categories	%
1970-1979	
International	100
Other African Nations	0
Tanzania	0
1980-1989	
International	85.7
Other African Nations	4.8
Tanzanian	9.5
1990-1999	
International	98.3
Other African Nations	1.7
Tanzania	0
2000-2009	
International	91.1
Other African Nations	5.4
Tanzania	3.6
2010-2019	
International	87.4
Other African Nations	4.4
Tanzania	8.2
2020-2024	
International	82.6

Other African Nations	5.8
Tanzania	11.6

Australian Case Study: Affiliation data

Scopus Search Query:

((TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archaeology AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(archeology AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND sahum) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND dispersal AND australia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(homo AND sapiens AND dispersal AND sahum)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCl") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ARTS") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MULT") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BlOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART")))

Table S29 Percentage of Aboriginal Australian, Australian, and international author affiliations listed on publications focusing on human origins research conducted in and on Australia from 1970 to 2024. Data sourced from Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>). The full list of affiliations can be found in *Supplementary Information 3 – Case Study Affiliation Data*.

Categories	%
1970-1979	
International	25
Australian	75
Aboriginal Australian	0
% Australian affiliations that are Aboriginal Australian	0
1980-1989	
International	50
Australian	50
Aboriginal Australian	0
% Australian affiliations that are Aboriginal Australian	0
1990-1999	
International	60
Australian	40
Aboriginal Australian	0
% Australian affiliations that are Aboriginal Australian	0
2000-2009	
International	67.9
Australian	31.3
Aboriginal Australian	0.7
% Australian affiliations that are Aboriginal Australian	2.0
2010-2019	
International	45.6
Australian	48.1
Aboriginal Australian	6.3
% Australian affiliations that are Aboriginal Australian	12.0
2020-2024	
International	30.6
Australian	51.9
Aboriginal Australian	17.5
% Australian affiliations that are Aboriginal Australian	25.2